

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE IN GEORGIAN TOUR OPERATORS' OFFERINGS

Gigi Kuparadze

Professor at Grigol Robakidze University

Niko Kvaratskhelia

Professor at Grigol Robakidze University

Erekle Ugrelidze

Associate Professor at Grigol Robakidze University

Sofio Lazishvili

Assistant at Grigol Robakidze University

Abstract

This study examines the role of intangible cultural heritage in the offerings of Georgian tour operators. Additionally, the research investigates the challenges faced by providers of intangible cultural heritage services. The study is based on qualitative research conducted with inbound tour operators and intangible cultural service providers in Tbilisi and Batumi. The results reveal the equal importance of both tangible and intangible heritage in Georgian inbound tour operators' offerings. The study identifies only partial utilization of Georgian monuments listed in UNESCO's World Intangible Cultural Heritage in tour operators' programs. It emphasizes the positive role of commercial activities related to intangible heritage in raising awareness about intangible cultural monuments. Overall, the study suggests that there is a need for greater promotion of intangible cultural heritage, education and awareness-raising among the public, efforts to increase the recognition of intangible cultural heritage, and establishing closer connections between tour operators and intangible cultural heritage service providers.

Keywords: Cultural tourism, inbound tourism, Georgian intangible cultural heritage.

Introduction

Georgia has traditionally been an attractive country for tourists, as evidenced by the statistics of visitors and tourists arriving in the country over the past decades. Due to the country's geographical, natural, cultural, and historical-ethnographic diversity, various forms and types of tourism are successfully developing in Georgia. It can be confidently stated that cultural tourism is the traditional and most attractive form for Georgia, with a long history. Based on research conducted in our country, as well as international experience, it can be boldly said that at least half of the international tourists coming to the country are cultural tourists. (G. Kuparadze, Cultural Tourism, Tbilisi, 2022)

However, regarding cultural tourism, as in many countries worldwide, there are many unanswered questions in Georgia as well. Specifically, how are cultural tourists accounted for? Is the statistics based on a broad, activity-based definition of cultural tourism, or a narrower, motivation-based definition is used? Which segment of cultural heritage represents a more significant attraction factor for international or domestic tourists? What are the main characteristics and current trends of the cultural market in Georgia? However, research and analysis of the tourist market is a necessary condition for providing correct recommendations to tour operators and tourist service providers. Unfortunately, there is an acute shortage of such research in Georgia. Moreover, in Georgia's reality, there is no research that would show the transformation of tourist firms' offerings in terms of the intensity of displaying intangible cultural heritage (ICH) over the past thirty years.

Review of Georgian and Foreign Literature

The following UNESCO publications on intangible cultural heritage were used to prepare the article:

1. UNESCO, Identifying and Inventorying Intangible Cultural Heritage, (URL: <https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/01856-EN.pdf>)

2. UNESCO, Guidance note for inventorying Intangible Cultural Heritage, 2017 (URL: <https://ich.unesco.org/en/guidance-note-on-inventorying-00966>)

3. UNESCO, Basic texts of the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage, 2022, (URL: https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/2003_Convention_Basic_Texts-2022_version-EN.pdf)

4. UNESCO, Toolkit for requesting International Assistance from the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage 2022 Edition (URL: <https://ich.unesco.org/doc/src/53724-EN.pdf>)

5. The United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) published a comprehensive study in 2012, which represents a baseline study on the connections between tourism and intangible cultural heritage (ICH). In addition to studying the main challenges, risks, and opportunities for the development of ICH-related tourism, it examines practical steps for developing, managing, and marketing tourism products based on intangible cultural heritage. (World Tourism Organization (2012), Tourism and Intangible Cultural Heritage, UNWTO, Madrid. URL: <https://www.unwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284414796>)

6. In a publication issued by the World Tourism Organization in 2018, which deals with the synergy of tourism and culture, a study is presented in which both

member states and experts participated. This study mainly concerns the share of cultural tourists in total tourist flows, the motivations of cultural tourists, and the importance of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. It also provides a new definition of cultural tourism. (World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), Tourism and Culture Synergies, 2018, URL: <https://www.unwto.org/doi/book/10.18111/9789284418978>)

Legislative acts adopted in Georgia regarding intangible cultural heritage:

1. National Agency for Cultural Heritage Preservation of Georgia, Registration Card for Intangible Cultural Heritage Object/Monument (URL: <https://www.heritagesites.ge/uploads/files/5b7e9011839d6.pdf>)

2. Resolution №303 of the Government of Georgia of July 1, 2016, "On Approval of Culture Strategy 2025" (URL: <https://www.matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/download/3328805/0/ge/pdf>)

3. On granting the status of an intangible cultural heritage monument to objects valuable from the perspective of cultural heritage. (URL: <https://matsne.gov.ge/ka/document/view/4897243?publication=0>)

Research Goal and Objectives

The goal of research is to analyze the offerings of intangible cultural heritage in programs prepared by Georgian tour operators for foreign tourists. In modern cultural tourism, the demonstration of intangible culture occupies an increasingly important place. If in the previous century priority was given to monuments of material culture, now the presentation of the nation's spiritual culture has become the primary goal of cultural tourism

The Essence of Intangible Cultural Heritage

Intangible cultural heritage is the knowledge and skills that are passed down from generation to generation and from person to person. Consequently, these forms of culture have an identity-forming effect. It is an opportunity to rediscover our cultural memory and, accordingly, the importance of communities, and not to stop at individualism and performance-oriented thinking. (Gigi Kuparadze, Niko Kvaratskhelia, Some aspects of historical connections from hydrothermal public baths to the modern spa industry, 2022)

Intangible cultural heritage is embodied in the practice, expressions, knowledge, and skills, as well as related objects and cultural spaces, which communities and individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage. Transmitted through generations and constantly recreated, it gives humanity a sense of identity and continuity. (World Tourism Organization, Tourism and Intangible Cultural Heritage, UNWTO, Madrid, 2012)

A study conducted by UNWTO in 2018 with the participation of member countries, found that the main priority in cultural tourism is product development. The most important aspect of this type of tourism product is tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

From the previous century to the present day, priority has been given to monuments of material culture,

especially in terms of recognition, but some experts of the World Tourism Organization believe that now the presentation of the nation's spiritual culture has become the primary goal of cultural tourism. It is especially noteworthy that intangible cultural heritage is considered as the most effective means of tourists' repeated travel (revisits). As stated in the UNWTO study, "Places with monuments of material cultural heritage attract visitors, but only once, unless this material heritage resembles the changing exhibitions of the Guggenheim. Probably very few people travel the world to see the Taj Mahal or the Alhambra twice. Thus, cultural tourism differs from trips aimed at seeing an attraction once and putting a 'plus'. Cultural tourism has much more to do with intangible heritage because it is more flexible than material heritage. The latter can evoke initial charm but it cannot create a sense of loyalty and deep connection." (World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), Tourism and Culture Synergies, 2018) Thus, in modern cultural tourism, the importance of intangible cultural heritage will steadily increase.

On the one hand, there is a growing interest in intangible cultural heritage, and on the other hand, there are no more or less convincing studies and proper market analysis. Therefore we, a small group of professors and students from Grigol Robakidze University's Tbilisi and Batumi representations, set a goal to contribute our small part to solving this problem and to study the programs of tour operators operating in two major tourist centers of Georgia, Tbilisi and Batumi, to determine how much attention they pay to intangible cultural heritage. We focused particularly on those inbound tour operators who are united in the Georgian Incoming Tour Operators Association (GITO). However, tourist companies that are members of the Georgian Tourism Association also participated in the study. In addition, we investigated providers of intangible cultural services (museums, art centers, Batumi Boulevard, Georgian dance and song ensembles, Tbilisi sulfur baths, and others).

Intangible Cultural Heritage as the Object for Tourism Investigation

The foundation of cultural tourism in Georgia is its tangible and intangible cultural heritage. As of September 2024, there are 7,942 registered immovable cultural heritage monuments in Georgia, 596 movable monuments, and only 72 intangible cultural heritage monuments. (National Agency for Cultural Heritage Preservation of Georgia, 2024) Such a small number of the latter is due to the slow pace of registration, the complexity of the registration forms, and other factors.

In Georgia's "Law on Tourism," Article 3 – "State Policy in the Field of Tourism" – Paragraph B states: "Determination of priority directions in tourism and development assistance." (Law of Georgia on Tourism, 2023) In our opinion, intangible cultural heritage should be a priority direction because what leaves a lasting impression on a tourist's memory is what they experience through all five senses.

Research Approaches

Qualitative research of tourist companies and cultural tourism service providers was carried out through two different pre-prepared questionnaires. As

an exception, several other in-depth interviews were conducted as well.

Research Progress and Results

The research was conducted in Tbilisi and Batumi, in two most popular tourist cities.

I. Results of Tour Operators' Survey in Tbilisi and Batumi:

1.1 To the first question: Which definition of intangible cultural heritage would you prefer?

a. Intangible heritage is the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills, as well as the instruments, objects, artifacts, and cultural spaces recognized by communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals as part of their cultural heritage.

b. Intangible heritage is crafts and folk crafts, gastronomy, traditional festivals, traditional music, oral traditions, religion.

The responses were equally divided 50/50:

It is interesting that in the case of Tbilisi, 64% sided with the UN Tourism definition.

1.2 If all responses to the question - "Which do you consider more important for your tourist programs?" from Tbilisi company representatives were unanimous,

and they gave equal importance to both tangible and intangible heritage, there was an exception in Batumi, according to one company representative, tangible heritage is superior.

For more clarity, it must be emphasized that none of the respondents gave priority to intangible cultural heritage.

1.3 To the question, "Do you agree with the statement: 'Probably very few people travel the world to see the Taj Mahal or the Alhambra twice. Cultural tourism

differs from trips aimed at seeing an attraction once and putting a 'plus'. Cultural tourism has much more to do with intangible heritage because it is more flexible than material heritage. The latter can evoke initial charm, but it cannot create a sense of loyalty and deep connection", the responses from Batumi and Tbilisi respondents were almost equally divided:

Agreed - 44%

Partially agreed - 56%

Disagreed – 0.

1.4 To the question - "Which of the Georgian intangible cultural monuments, included in the UNESCO World Heritage List, are included in your programs?"

- Georgian polyphonic singing
- Georgian alphabet
- Georgian method of wine-making in Qvevri
- Georgian wrestling

The responses were distributed as follows:

Note: It was possible to circle several answers to this question.

1.5 To the question "In your opinion, can public centers, museums, archives, and other similar objects play a positive role in raising awareness about intangible cultural heritage?"

- They can
- They can but to a small extent
- They cannot

In this case, almost all respondents from Batumi and Tbilisi noted that public centers, museums, archives, and other similar objects can play a positive role in raising awareness about intangible cultural heritage. There was one exception in Batumi, who circled answer „b“ - "They can, but to a small extent".

1.6 To the question - "What role can formal and non-formal education play in raising awareness about the importance of intangible cultural heritage? What kind of educational materials can be developed for this purpose?"

All tour operators, both from Tbilisi and Batumi, confirmed that the proper functioning of the education system can play a positive role in raising awareness about intangible cultural heritage. Different opinions were recorded about the role of formal and non-formal education, but the balance still tipped towards formal education.

1.7 To the question - "In your opinion, can commercial activities related to intangible heritage contribute to raising awareness about the importance of intangible cultural monuments?"

In answering this question, all respondents, both in Batumi and Tbilisi, were unanimous. Everyone believes that commercial activity more or less contributes to raising awareness about the importance of intangible cultural monuments.

1.8 To the question - "In your opinion, what are the hindering factors due to which intangible cultural monuments cannot be adequately used in cultural tourism?"

Unfortunately, a wide range of problems emerged in the answers, although according to tour operator representatives, the primary problem is still the low qualification of service providers and the low quality of service. For example, here are some answers:

- "Scarcity of service providers and high prices for quality products"
- "The main reason why intangible cultural monuments cannot be adequately used is the low quality of service. As a rule, this intangible culture is represented by individuals living in high mountain regions who have little contact with the service sector."
- "Low qualification of those employed in tourism; failure to understand the essence of tourism."
- "Lack of quality tourist product. For example, in the case of festivals - constant change of dates. Also lack of education"
- "Lack of information and offerings about intangible heritage".
- Absence of a guide certification system.

1.9 To the question - "In your opinion, what issues should the relevant state structures focus on to promote the development of cultural tourism, including interest in intangible cultural monuments?"

• There were two main issues in the answers received from Batumi. One, which we wrote about in the case of Tbilisi as well - "More educational programs need to be introduced", and the second problem was not particularly emphasized in the responses received from Tbilisi:

- "Organize folk festivals, concerts, shows, etc."
- "Conduct frequent festivals and events, as well as trainings".

II. Results of ICH Service Providers Survey

Providers of tourist services containing intangible cultural heritage were surveyed in Tbilisi and Batumi: museums, Georgian folk dance and song ensembles, Tbilisi sulfur baths, Batumi Boulevard, and other organizations.

2.1 To the first question - "Does your institution's profile allow for the inclusion of ICH elements in the tourist product?", all answers were positive.

2.2 The second question was formulated as follows: "Give some examples of including ICH elements in the tourist product".

Among the examples given, the Adjara Cultural Heritage Protection Agency, Adjara Art Museum, and Tbilisi Giorgi Chitaia Open Air Museum of Ethnography stand out.

Adjara Art Museum has provided five examples:

1. Classical music evenings, once a week, at the same time
2. Ballerina show - the interior allows for this, and foreigners especially like it
3. Painting, ceramics, felting masterclass and sale of works at auction
4. Portrait performance - show of living portraits, opportunity to try on costumes
5. Gen Z - quest-type intellectual game for young visitors.

The public legal entity Batumi Boulevard events include: folklore evenings, masterclasses, dance performances.

Adjara Cultural Heritage Protection Agency events include:

1. Video clip presentation at the Alphabet Tower: This event incorporated Adjara's embroidery traditions (ICH monument since 2019). Embroidery masters were embroidering on-site using various techniques.

2. Organized by the agency, an exhibition of cultural heritage monuments of Adjara and Abkhazia was held at the "Intourist Hotel". An integral part of the event was Adjarian cuisine, represented by the traditional dish "Borano" (which has ICH status).

3. The agency permanently organizes various events in buildings with cultural monument status, promotes the dissemination of information about monuments. Also, decorative art (embroidery, crafts) or culinary products are always included in the events as props.

Folklore events of the Giorgi Chitaia Tbilisi Ethnographic Museum include:

1. Initiative of the ensemble "Didgori", which earned great public interest and additionally attracted both foreign and Georgian visitors to the museum. The folklore program of the museum was also supplemented by Georgian dance concerts of the ensemble "Potskhishvili". In 2024, "Didgori" and "Potskhishvili" were granted the status of ensemble of the Giorgi Chitaia Ethnographic Museum.

2. Ethnographic theater. Since 2023, historical and ethnographic themed performances and premiere shows are held at various regional houses in the museum.

3. Restoration of the tradition of celebrating Tbilisoba in the museum with the participation of regions. In 2022, the tradition of celebrating Tbilisoba was restored on the museum's territory. At the Tbilisoba festival, all regions of Georgia, including Abkhazia and Samachablo (South Ossetia Administration), presented ethnographic performances and exhibitions, folklore, culinary masterclasses, and wine characteristic of their regions.

4. Traditional Georgian craft masterclasses. In 2022, the craft school was renewed at the Tbilisi Ethnographic Museum. Within the framework of the renewed project, masterclasses are held seasonally, every spring and autumn.

5. Bread baking masterclasses in the tone (traditional Georgian bread oven). In the autumn of 2024, masterclasses for baking Georgian shoti bread in the tone were restored in the museum, in which museum visitors actively participate.

6. Opening of a professional blacksmith school. In November 2023, a professional blacksmith school was opened at the G. Chitaia Tbilisi Ethnographic Museum. The program is led by blacksmith Zakaria Bakuradze. Within the framework of the project, people of different professions, interested in blacksmithing, will study Georgian blacksmithing techniques and acquire blacksmithing as a new profession. The four-month course includes 32 lessons.

The Georgian Folk Song and Instrument Museum of the Art Palace focuses on folk songs, folk dances, and Georgian cuisine.

2.3 Third question – "What ICH elements could be included in the tourist product in the future?"

The following dominate among the answers:

- Folk song;
- Folk dance;
- Georgian cuisine;
- Medicinal sulfur waters and accompanying massage and kisa (traditional bath scrubbing);
- Revival of old Georgian holidays;
- Revitalization of various regional homesteads with costumed ethnographic performances.

2.4 Fourth question – "What problems do service provider organizations face when dealing with ICH issues for tourists?"

The following answers were recorded:

- Lack of interest from tourist agencies;
- Scarcity of budget (this is a concern for budgetary organizations);

- Lack of marketing strategy in terms of ICH;
- Scarcity or absence of human resources;
- Absence of databases of ICH providers;
- Incorrect priorities of tourist agencies when planning tours. Often guides and tourist companies choose locations for tourists from which guides will receive more so-called cashback, i.e., they will get back a percentage of the paid amount and have more income.

2.5 Fifth question-"What measures need to be taken to more actively involve ICH in tourist activities?"

The answers focused on the following issues:

- Organizing info-tours for tour operators and guides;
- Cooperation with tourist organizations;
- More advertising and use of various advertising means;
- Raising awareness;
- Searching for suppliers of elements of ICH and making an agreement with them.

Conclusions

The analysis of the results of our research allows us to formulate several conclusions:

- Regarding intangible cultural heritage, its presentation and interpretation, and current trends in the international market, there is a need to raise their level of awareness which can be supplemented by organizing various business meetings, sharing experiences of foreign experts, and providing free information;
- In many cases, the connection between tour operators and ICH service providers is weak or non-existent. Accordingly, care is needed to establish and strengthen cluster connections;
- In most of the tourist programs of Georgian tour operator companies, two of the four monuments included in the UNESCO Intangible Cultural Heritage List are actively presented (Georgian polyphonic singing and the Georgian method of wine-making in Qvevri), while the other two (Georgian alphabet and Georgian wrestling) are presented only in rare cases. Perhaps more information is needed on what is the reason for this and support to ensure that both the alphabet and wrestling should be more included in tourist programs;
- From the answers of both tour operators and providers, it was unequivocally revealed that more promotion of intangible cultural heritage and raising awareness is needed;
- Raising the level of education and awareness of society and care for increasing the recognition of ICH also emerged as an important issue;
- The research revealed that museums are relatively more interested in ICH products than other types of objects and individuals whose services include ICH elements. Museums try to introduce ICH products to tourists on their own initiative;

- It is important to find, register, and connect ICH element providers with tour operators.

To address the above-mentioned challenges, first of all, it is necessary to interest the Georgian National Tourism Administration and the Ministry of Culture and Sports of Georgia in this direction and take appropriate measures.

The interest and activity of the Ministry of Education, Science and Youth of Georgia, as well as state and private universities, will be important in solving certain problems.

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